

Interaction of Hot and Thermal F^{18} Atoms with Trans-1-Fluoro-2-Chloroethylene*

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A study of the isomeric transformations of trans-1-fluoro, 2-chloroethylene as a result of the hot interaction of high-energetic fluorine-18 atoms resulting from the nuclear reaction $F^{19}(n, 2n)F^{18}$ has been done. The ratio of cis- $CHF^{18} = CHF$ /trans- $CHF^{18} = CHF$ was found to be constant and equal to 1.2 and is independent of the pressure in the irradiation sample. A full-scale description was already given to the way that hot F^{18} atoms interact with the parent compound;— the gradual electronic involvement giving rise to the total torsion of H branch about the C-C axis to counterbalance the mass center shift with the instant ejection of the heaviest of all chlorine atom. The presence of ethylene, HI and neon was not able to shift this ratio. In the presence of C_2H_4 and HI the rate of adding one hydrogen atom to the excited $CH_2F^{18}CH_2$ radical is much faster than the rate of ejecting one H atom by the same radical. Therefore, the yield of $CH_2F^{18}-CH_3$ is considerably larger than the yield of $CHF^{18} = CH_2$.

A plot of the ratios of $CH_2F^{18}-CH_3/CHF^{18} = CH_2$ against the SF_6/C_2H_4 pressures has been found to be linear and directly proportional to it. The percentage yield of $CH_2F^{18}-CH_3$, contrary to that of $CHF^{18} = CH_2$, increases as the pressure of SF_6 (fluorine atoms supplier) increases. Among the thermal products $CHClF^{18}-CH_2F$ has been identified. The excited $CHClF^{18}C^*HF$ radical formed by the thermal addition of F^{18} to the parent compound competes most likely with $CH_2F^{18}-C^*H_2$ radical, formed by the addition of thermal F^{18} to the double bond of ethylene molecule.

A study of the gas phase reaction of 1-fluoro, 2-chloroethylene has been done utilizing the nuclear reaction $F^{19}(n, 2n)F^{18}$ and SF_6 as a source of fluorine atoms. A sealed tube fast neutron generator was the source for 14 MeV. fast neutrons. The cis/trans difluoroethylene (labeled by F^{18}) ratio has been found to be equal to 1.2 regardless of the pressure of SF_6 , the presence of some additives like $CH_2 = CH_2$, and the radical scavenger HI.

Further evidence for the mechanism of the formation of vinyl fluoride ($C_2H_3F^{18}$) by the addition of a thermalized F^{18} atom to the double bond of ethylene with the successive elimination of one hydrogen atom has been presented by this work. In the presence of HI the formation of fluoroethane ($CH_3-CH_2F^{18}$) has a considerable favor over the formation of $C_2H_3F^{18}$, evidently because the rate of scavenging (trapping) of one hydrogen atom is much faster than the rate of eliminating it:

Reactions (1) and (2) take place both in the presence and absence of HI, contrary to reaction (3),

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which only occurs in the presence of hydrogen iodide. The ratio $CH_3-CH_2F^{18}/C_2H_3F^{18}$ increases with increasing SF_6/C_2H_4 pressures (in cm. Hg) and the dependence of the first upon the second has been found to be linear.

It seems, so far, very difficult to explain why the yield of the cis-difluoroethylene- F^{18} is larger than the yield of the trans isomer since the dissociation energy of C-Cl bond is much less than the dissociation energy of C-H and C-F bonds.

Experimental

Energetic F^{18} atoms has been formed by the nuclear reaction $F^{19}(n, 2n)F^{18}$ occurring with the fluorine atoms of SF_6 as a target. The radioactive F^{18} -labeled products were analyzed by the usual procedures of radio gas chromatography^{1,2}. Two columns were used: 20 feet Silicone Oil for the separation of the parent compound (trans $CHCl-CHF$) and $CHClF^{18}-CH_2F$. The second column was 50 feet DMS for the separation of vinyl fluoride- F^{18} and the trans $CHF^{18} = CHF$.

Time was allowed for the decay of C^{11} ($T_{1/2} = 20.4$ min.)³ and corrections were made for the F^{18} decay ($A = A_0e^{-\lambda t}$) to the whole activity of each peak, considering the end of the irradiation of the ampoule as zero time.

A gas chromatography separation and purification of the trans 1-fluoro, 2-chloroethylene isomer was made. Further gas chromatography test has shown

minor impurities (0.1%). Fig. 1 shows the infrared spectrum of trans 1-fluoro, 2-chloroethylene. This identification has been confirmed referring to the IR spectra given in (4).

Pyrex ampoules (about 10 ml.) have been evacuated and filled with the reactants at different pressures. Hydrogen iodide was added to some samples at its vapor pressure and at room temperature (25°). After sealing, ampoules have been irradiated at constant flux (170 Kv) and constant beam (2.5–3 mA) for 15 min.s.

Identification (+) of labeled by-F¹⁸—products was made with the aid of a high efficiency thin-window flow counter working in the proportional region, connected directly to the outlet of the separation column.

Results and Discussion

In addition to SF₆ and the parent compound (trans 1-fluoro 2-chloroethylene), HI (at its vapor pressure) and ethylene were present in the system to act as scavengers for F¹⁸ atoms reached thermal energies) without reaction. HI serves also as a source for supplying hydrogen atoms, the importance of which will be demonstrated later. The presence of some oxygen (4 cm. Hg) reduced the total activity by one order of magnitude (first and second samples), while the presence of some ethylene in the ratio SF₆/C₂H₄ = 36.5 reduced the total activity of the sample by a factor of six (first and the fifth samples—Table 1). Further reduction of the total activity was achieved by the presence of 80 cm. Hg neon (fourth sample).

(+) F¹⁸ emits B⁺ and B⁻. Total E = 1.249 MeV.

$T_{1/2} = 104.7$ min.

No special efforts were made to trace and detect as hot products the FF¹⁸ emitted from excited SF₅F¹⁸ or rather formed from it by the fast one-step energetic abstraction of one fluorine atom by hot F¹⁸.

No attempt to find HF¹⁸ was made either, assuming that it is the product of the abstraction of one hydrogen atom from ethylene or the parent molecule itself. FF¹⁸ will⁽⁵⁾ either go to the wall and bound there, or react with the added CH₂ = CH₂ to form C₂H₄FF¹⁸. The latter highly excited molecule might decompose to yield either HF or HF¹⁸, both of which are supposed to be absorbed by the glass walls of the ampoule. N. Colebourne *et al.*⁵ gave an estimation of 2.5–10% as the magnitude of the untrapped FF¹⁸.

Part I

DMS column

Hot Products :

Cis/trans ratio

The most striking results are those concerning the higher yield of the cis-difluoroethylene (labeled by F-18) compared with the trans isomer which retains the original geometric configuration. More striking is the constancy of the ratio cis-F¹⁸/trans-F¹⁸ in all conditions, and its independence of the pressure of the sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) or the total pressure. Except that at very low SF₆/C₂H₄ ratio (0.15) the complete elimination of both isomers had occurred. The same thing had been observed in the presence of oxygen at very high pressure. The

Fig 1 IR SPECTRA OF TRANS - CHCl = CHF
WAVENUMBER CM^{-1}

value of 1.2 represents the average of 9 different experiments, and fig. 2 shows the plots of cis/trans ratio against the total pressure in cms. Hg. The following scheme illustrates the mechanism which accounts for the formation of the trans isomer, apparently by one-step displacement of the chlorine atom with full retention of the essential configuration :

Equation 5 show the schematic interpretation of the formation of cis-difluoroethylene-F¹⁸ (C) as a result of the interaction of hot recoiling F¹⁸ atoms with the parent compound.

It suggests that the rate of rotation (or distortion) about C-C bond is much faster than the rate of decomposition of the excited intermediate radical (a). Experiments of C. Wai and Rowland⁶ confirm the rapidity of rotation about C-C bond in CHCl¹⁸ClCHCl radical. Others⁽⁷⁾ have reported that the radical intermediates appear to have free rotation in their experiments; or^{8,9} even used free rotation models in unimolecular reaction rate calculations.

There is no chance to think that the formation of the trans isomer and the cis-difluoroethylene isomer take place in a similar mechanism, though both of them occur in the hot region of interaction (3-100 eV). The higher yield of the cis/isomer gives the impression that the 'twist' process about C-C bond occurs within lower energetic limits of interaction than does the substitution process of F¹⁸ for one Cl atom, and, thus resulting in the formation of the more stable isomer (the cis one). The absolute absence of CClF¹⁸ = CHF (one hydrogen atom being displaced by one hot F¹⁸ atom) in our experiments contradicts the results and conclusions of Spicer *et al.*¹⁰, who stated that not only because the hydrogen atoms are small, but also because their vibrational relaxation times are short or comparable to the time of the collision, thus can adiabatically adjust to the incoming halogen atom and to be displaced by it. One can explain the higher yield of the cis-isomer by suggesting that the thermal addition of F¹⁸ to the double bond of 1-fluoro, 2-chloroethylene may result in the formation of the cis-isomer (the more stable one), assuming that the mechanism of the hot interaction (eq. 5) is still to some extent valid for the thermal one. But it is unreal since the presence of a strong competitive compound (like ethylene) even at very high pressure does not affect the ratio of cis/trans. The presence of HI also does not influence this ratio. It is very clear that the presence of HI will result in the formation of CHClF¹⁸.CH₂F by the second-step addition of one H atom to the excited intermediate radical CHClF¹⁸.CHF. This question can only be clarified if it was possible to have the exact ratio of CHClF¹⁸ = CH₂F/cis-CHF¹⁸ = CHF over different pressures of SF₆, HI, and the parent compound.

Fig. 2 TOTAL PRESS. - Cm. Hg.

Fig. 2. A plot of the total pressure in cms. Hg of each sample against the cis-CHF¹⁸ = CHF/trans-CHF¹⁸ = CHF ratio, labeled by -F¹⁸ products as a result of the hot interaction of F¹⁸ atoms with trans-1-fluoro, 2-chloroethylene compound in the gas phase.

The elasticity and the symmetry of the trans-1-fluoro, 2-chloroethylene molecule serves as a flexible absorbent for the energetic attacking F^{18} atom. Thus, overcoming the coulombic repulsive forces it finds itself confined in the electronic atmosphere of the attacked molecule (eq. 5, *a, b*, and *c*). The incident kinetic energy of F^{18} is evidently insufficient to knock out and replace the chlorine atom, owing to the large difference in the atomic masses of F^{18} and Cl (35.5) atoms. Therefore F^{18} can only push Cl atom forwardly. As Cl atom approaches H atom opposite to it (eq. 5-*a*), the mass center of the whole parent molecule is disturbed and the unsatisfied molecule readjusts itself by a rapid rotation of the H branch about the C-C bond to attain a stable and balanced symmetrical state of the cis isomer. This 'long' operation does not last more than 10^{-10} sec.⁽⁶⁾, a small fraction of time which is shorter than the life-time of the intermediate radical $CHClF^{18}\cdot C^{\cdot}HF$ (eq. 5-*a*).

Part II

Thermal Products :

The plot of this ratio against the ratio of the pressures of $SF_6/CH_2=CH_2$ has a linear character (Fig. 3). As a matter of fact this means that the

Fig 3 $CH_3-CH_2F^{18}/CH_2=CHF^{18}$

Fig. 3. A plot of SF_6/C_2H_4 ratio in cms. Hg against

ratio, labeled by $-F^{18}$ products as a result of the interaction of the thermalized F^{18} atoms with ethylene molecules in the presence of 3 cm. Hg HI at room temperature and at its vapor pressure.

yield of fluoroethane- F^{18} depends on the pressure of SF_6 . The more SF_6 present in the sample, the more is the yield of $CH_3-CH_2F^{18}$. Or, conversely, the more ethylene present, the more is the yield of the competing vinyl fluoride- F^{18} ($CH_2=CHF^{18}$), and the less is the alternative yield of $CH_3-CH_2F^{18}$. Generally, the decomposition rate of excited CH_2F^{18} radicals rises sharply with increasing pressure of SF_6 , but in such a way which is substantially

different from that reported in equation (2). Otherwise, one must expect an adequate increase in the yield of vinyl fluoride- F^{18} (Figs. 3, 4, 5 and Table 1).

Fig. 4 $SF_5F^{18}/CH_2=CHF^{18}$

Fig. 4. A plot of SF_6/C_2H_4 ratio in cms. Hg against

ratio, labeled by F^{18} products as a result of the interaction of F^{18} atoms with ethylene and SF_6 molecules (the source of F^{18} atoms).

Fig 5 SF_6/C_2H_4 - C m. Hg.

Fig. 5. Plot of the percentage yield of $CH_3-CH_2F^{18}$, products of the thermal addition of F^{18} atoms to the double bond of ethylene molecules, against the ratio of SF_6/C_2H_4 pressures in cms. Hg. Total activity of each sample regarded as equal to 100.

TABLE I.

The activity (total counts/peaks) of the labeled by -F-¹⁸ products as a result of different mechanistic interaction of F¹⁸ atoms with trans-CHCl = CHF and CH₂ = CH₂. Some samples contained HI or O₂ or Ne. This table shows also ratios of cis-CHF¹⁸ = CHF/trans-CHF¹⁸ = CHF, column used : 50 feet DMS at 0°

Sample	Reactants	Pressure -cm.Hg-	Total Press.	Products	Activity A ₀	$\frac{\text{cis-CHF}^{18} = \text{CHF}}{\text{trans-CHF}^{18} = \text{CHF}}$	$\frac{\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2\text{F}^{18}}{\text{CH}_2 = \text{CHF}^{18}}$	$\frac{\text{SF}_6/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}{\text{-cm.Hg-}}$	$\frac{\text{SF}_6\text{F}^{18}}{\text{CH}_2 = \text{CHF}^{18}}$	Total activity of each sample
1	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF SF ₆	5 351	356	SF ₆ F ¹⁸ <i>t</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF ???	12428 125693 933 163519	1.30	—	—	—	302573
2	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF SF ₆ O ₂	5 37 4	46	SF ₆ F ¹⁸ ???	617 296 13889 17209	1.24	—	—	—	32011
3	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF SF ₆ CH ₂ = CH ₂	4.9 71.4 9.1	85	SF ₆ F ¹⁸ CH ₂ = CHF ¹⁸ <i>t</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF <i>c</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF	1229 6655 4147 4958	1.17	—	7.80 ÷ ÷ ÷ ÷	0.18	16889
4	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF SF ₆ CH ₂ = CH ₂ Ne	10 38.6 10 80	138.6	SF ₆ F ¹⁸ CH ₂ = CHF ¹⁸ <i>t</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF <i>c</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF	334 2725 2779 3228	1.16	—	3.86	0.11	9066
5	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF SF ₆ CH ₂ = CH ₂	5 339.6 9.3	354	SF ₆ F ¹⁸ CH ₂ = CHF ¹⁸ <i>t</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF <i>c</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF	8367 8204 15081 18564	1.23	—	36.5	1.20	50116
6	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF SF ₆ CH ₂ = CH ₂ HI	5 10.6 70.9 3	89.5	SF ₆ F ¹⁸ CH ₂ = CHF ¹⁸ <i>t</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF CH ₃ -CH ₂ F ¹⁸ ???	— 1856 — 2522 434	—	1.4	0.15	—	61986
7	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF SF ₆ CH ₂ = CH ₂ HI	5 27.3 39.5 3	74.8	SF ₆ F ¹⁸ CH ₂ = CHF ¹⁸ <i>t</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF CH ₃ -CH ₂ F ¹⁸ ???	196 3602 106 8366 199	1.50	2.3	0.69	0.054	12605
				<i>c</i> -CHF ¹⁸ = CHF	156					

TABLE I (Contd.)

Sample	Reactants	Pressure 2 cm. Hg.	Total Press.	Products	Activity A_0	$\frac{\text{cis-CHF}_{18} = \text{CHF}}{\text{trans-CHF}_{18} = \text{CHF}}$	$\frac{\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2\text{F}_{18}}{\text{CH}_2 = \text{CHF}_{18}}$	$\frac{\text{SF}_6/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}{\text{-cm. Hg.}} \cdot \frac{\text{SF}_6\text{F}_{18}}{\text{CH}_2 = \text{CHF}_{18}}$	Total Activity of each sample
8	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF	23.4	65	SF ₆ F ₁₈	309	0.95	3.1	1.5	25462
	SF ₆	23.1		???	777				
	CH ₂ = CH ₂	15.5		CH ₂ = CHF ₁₈	3983				
	HI	3		<i>t</i> -CHF ₁₈ = CHF	4255				
				CH ₃ -CH ₂ F ₁₈	12368				
			<i>c</i> -CHF ₁₈ = CHF	3770					
9	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF	6.3	90	SF ₆ F ₁₈	826	0.99	7	5.8	46280
	SF ₆	68.8		CH ₂ = CHF ₁₈	5046				
	CH ₂ = CH ₂	11.9		<i>t</i> -CHF ₁₈ = CHF	2656				
	HI	3		CH ₃ -CH ₂ F ₁₈	35113				
				<i>c</i> -CHF ₁₈ = CHF	2639				
10	<i>t</i> -CHCl = CHF	5	264.5	SF ₆ F ₁₈	7813	1.37	33.6	21.3	382364
	SF ₆	245		CH ₂ = CHF ₁₈	10700				
	CH ₂ = CH ₂	11.5		<i>t</i> -CHF ₁₈ = CHF	10687				
	HI	3		CH ₃ -CH ₂ F ₁₈	336704				
				???	1435				
			<i>c</i> -CHF ₁₈ = CHF	15025					

Contrary to the observations of Wolfgang *et al.*¹, CH₃-CH₂F¹⁸ can only be observed in the presence of both HI (3 cm. Hg) and ethylene, while vinyl fluoride-F¹⁸ appears usually as a result of the thermal interaction of the thermalized F¹⁸ atoms (after many successive collisions with the surrounding molecules) with ethylene, most probably by the addition to its double bond with the simultaneous elimination of one hydrogen atom (equations 1 and 2). The resulting CH₂F¹⁸-CH₂ radical forms with an excitation energy of about 60 Kcal. (1). Introducing a proton-donor as HI in a small ratio decreases the rate of decomposition of the excited intermediate radical CH₂F¹⁸-CH₂ and, thus enhances the rate of formation of CH₃-CH₂F¹⁸ by the much faster addition mechanism of H atom to the still unsaturated carbon atom of the carbene group (CH₂). Since the ultimate yield of CH₃-CH₂F¹⁸ is independent of the pressure of ethylene, there is no way even to think that its formation may take place according to the following mechanism :

Therefore, there is only the way explained earlier (eqs. 1, 2, and 3), which finds its significance through the decomposition—addition process of CH₂F¹⁸-CH₂ radical. So, the ratio of K_2/K_1 linearly depends upon the increasing value of SF₆/C₂H₄ (Fig. 3).

The nature of reaction of hydrogen atom with CH₂F¹⁸-CH₂ radical is still to the best knowledge of the author, unknown. It may be the sequence of the direct reaction of HI with this radical, or perhaps the combination of it with free hydrogen atoms splitted off the HI in the irradiation course under the dissociating radiations (H-I bond dissociation energy = 70.5 Kcal). Anyway, observations based on our results confirm that the interaction first takes place between F¹⁸ atoms and ethylene, while the interaction which comes later must be between H atoms and CH₂F¹⁸-CH₂ radical.

The activation energy for reaction (3) seems to be very low compared with that for reaction (2), where its activation energy must be more than 40 Kcal. Fig. 5 shows another plot of the percentage yield of CH₃-CH₂F¹⁸ and CH₂=CHF¹⁸ (total activity regarded as equal to 100) against the ratio of pressures of SF₆/C₂H₄. Unlike results of (5), concerning the same plot of the percentage yield of C₂H₃F¹⁸ and C₂H₄F¹⁸I (which is analogous to our CH₃-CH₂F¹⁸ by combining an additional one hydrogen atom instead of the iodine atom) against CF₄ pressure (the source of F atoms), the two curves do not intersect at all. They do not meet each other either, even at very small ratio of SF₆/C₂H₄ (0.15). CH₃-CH₂F¹⁸ yield increases while that of C₂H₃F¹⁸ decreases with increasing SF₆/C₂H₄ ratio. Fig. 4 shows the linear dependence of the yield of vinyl fluoride-F¹⁸ upon ethylene pressure.

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